

An Analysis of Tourist Satisfaction in Cultural and Environmental Aspects of the Buon Ma Thuot Coffee Festival

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 01, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Coffee, Satisfaction, Festival</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5368883</p>	<p><i>This paper aimed at analyzing tourist satisfaction of cultural values and environmental aspects of the Buon Ma Thuot Coffee Festival (BCF). We found that tourists were highly satisfied with most of the cultural attributes but were disappointed with most environmental attributes at the BCF. Therefore, we suggested the BCF strategy should be revised by taking into account the tourists' benefits and achievability and measures should be taken to maintain or enhance the cultural attributes and eliminate weaknesses regarding the environment of the BCF.</i></p>

Introduction

One of the most important considerations for a festival is the satisfaction of the visitors. While definitions of satisfaction have been used in academic papers, it is generally recognized as a post-purchase construct relating to how much a consumer likes or dislikes a service or product after experiencing or using it (Woodside, Frey and Daly 1989). Pizam, Neumann, and Reichel (1978) measured tourist satisfaction based on a comparison between a tourist's experience and his or her expectations about the event destination. Moutinho (1987) emphasized that this post-purchase construct is primarily a function of pre-travel expectations and travel experiences. The attractiveness of a destination mirrors the feelings, beliefs, and opinions that a tourist has about a destination (Hu and Richie 1993). Mayo emphasized that the image of a destination region is a very important factor in the destination choice process (Mayo 1973). A lot of previous research has suggested that service quality impacts satisfaction directly. The higher the service quality is, the more satisfaction is obtained. However, some research has suggested that service quality may be only one of the determinants of satisfaction. A customer's overall satisfaction may be connected to their assessment of service quality, product features, and price as well (Parasuraman et al. 1994). Soutar suggested that satisfaction is a result of both service quality and the net value obtained. Thus, any measure of satisfaction needs to take the price into account (Soutar 2001).

In this paper, we emphasized the cultural and environmental aspects of a coffee festival in Buon Ma Thuot city, Dak Lak province of Vietnam, and measured the tourists' satisfaction using the HOLSAT model to identify the gaps between visitors' expectations and their actual perceptions as well as draw suggestions to improve the quality of the festival.

The Coffee Festival of Buon Ma Thuot City, Dak Lak Province of Vietnam

The Coffee Festival of Buon Ma Thuot City (the BCF) is a portfolio of events held every two years in Buon Ma Thuot City of Dak Lak province, Vietnam. This is a relatively large festival recognized by the Prime Minister of Vietnam as a 'national level' festival. The festival aims to recognize the importance of coffee trees, which occupy a significant position in the crop structure in the Central Highlands, accounting for 60% of Vietnam's total coffee output. The festival began to be held in 2005, as a program promoting the image of this city as the 'coffee capital' of Vietnam. The events involve activities concerning the production, and processing of coffee, as well as cultural and sports activities. In addition, the festival is also an opportunity to honor the dedication and hard work of coffee farmers and coffee traders. BCF is organized as a fair trade combined with many diverse, attractive, and rich activities that are aimed at contributing to attracting investment and attention from domestic and international tourists to Dak Lak Province (Dak Lak Provincial Committee 2019).

Table 1 presented the BCF's duration, main themes, and a portfolio of events at the BCF seven times. The BCF often took place for a week with the main themes varying from specific subjects associated with coffee production and trading to more abstract ones linking with the spirit of the mountains and forests. More events were added to the later organizations of the BCF to enrich the festival aiming at attracting more visitors to the festival.

Table 1. Portfolio of events during the Buon Ma Thuot Coffee Festivals

Items	1 st BCF	2 nd BCF	3 rd BCF	4 th BCF	5 th BCF	6 th BCF	7 th BCF
Year	2005	2008	2011	2013	2015	2017	2019
Duration	1 week	1 week	1 week	1 week	1 week	1 week	1 week
Main Themes	Geographic Id. on of the BMT coffee	A global BMT coffee Brand	The Breaths of Jungles	Linkages and Sustainable Devt.	Historic Spring Roads	Quintessence Convergence	The Quintessence from Jungles
Portfolio of Events							
-Fairs and exhibitions	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
-Conferences	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
-Farmers' contest	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
-Vietnamese Charms Performance	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no
- 'Coffee says' Performance	no	no	yes	no	no	no	no
-Coffee Tours	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
-Coffee Brewing Contests	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
-Elephant Race	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
-Log-canoe Race	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes

Source: The Dak Lak Department of Culture, Sports and Tourism

Method

Data

The collection of data was conducted using a questionnaire from 9th to 16th March 2019 in Buon Ma Thuot City. The target sample was domestic and foreign tourists participating in the festival. A sample was randomly drawn from the tourists from both organized tours and individuals who arrived at the festival. Tourists were asked to complete the questionnaire during and after the festival. We distributed 425 survey questionnaires to foreign travelers to the BCF and received 410 replies. After eliminating incomplete replies, 384 questionnaires were coded for data analysis.

Method

The model HOLSAT was used to measure the satisfaction of tourists with their vacation experience regarding cultural and environmental aspects of the BCF. Tourists were asked to rate the expectation of each attribute (before traveling) and rate perceptions or experiences (after traveling). A Likert scale is used to score each attribute in both "expectations" and "experiences" (Thuy-Huong&Foster 2006). The difference in the average score between the "expectations" and the "experiences" for each attribute provides a directional measure of visitors' satisfaction. Particularly, the tourists to the BCF were asked to rate their expectations before their arrivals for the BCF and their experiences during/ after the BCF event on a 5-point Likert scale. The scale was labeled and scored: strongly disagree (-4), disagree (-2), no opinion (0), agree (+2), and strongly agree (+4). Mean scores of the expectations and experiences were calculated and then derived the means differences between the expectations and experiences for each attribute item. By comparing the means of expectations and experiences, the level of tourist satisfaction was measured.

Results and Discussion

Using tools of the HOLSAT model, we designed 8 questions to ask for tourists' expectations and perceptions regarding the positive attributes of the BCF. These questions were used to measure the tourist satisfaction of cultural aspects during the BCF. All positive attributes were related to the cultural aspects as we expected that their values significantly contributed directly to the success of the BCF. We used 5 questions to collect tourist expectations and experiences regarding the negative attributes of the BCF regarding environments. It is worth

noting that all of these negative attributes were related to environmental aspects because it is expected to be easier to eliminate the negative side than to improve the positive side of the environment. For each attribute, a visitor's satisfaction or dissatisfaction is measured by comparing his or her expectations and perceptions. The data for analysis includes 384 domestic and foreign tourists to the BCF in 2019. The demographic profiling of respondents was presented in Table 2.

As shown in Table 2, about a half of respondents were domestic tourists and 53.6 % of them were males. Most of the tourists participate in the BCF for a pure tourism purpose (n = 272, 70.8 percent), a few are looking for business opportunities (n = 112, 29.2%). The majority of respondents traveled to Buon Ma Thuot as independent travelers (n = 300, 78.1 percent), whilst some said that they traveled on a package tour (n = 84, 21.9 percent).

Table 2. Demographic profiling of respondents

Demographic Variables	Categories	Number	%
Gender	Male	206	53.6
	Female	178	46.4
Age	18 - 25	83	21.6
	26 - 35	148	38.5
	36 - 50	123	32.0
	Above 50	30	7.8
Places of origin	Domestic	224	58.3
	Foreign	160	41.7
Occupation	Businessman	110	28.6
	Self-employed	48	12.5
	Teacher	33	8.6
	Farmer/ peasant	30	7.8
	Manual worker	52	13.5
	Other	111	28.9
Trip purpose	Pure tourism	272	70.8
	Business opportunities	112	29.2
Source of information	Friends/ Relatives	145	37.8
	Travel Agency	75	19.5
	Newspaper/ Magazine	48	12.5
	Advertisement	60	15.6
	Television	41	10.7
	Social Media	64	16.7
	Other	33	8.6

Source: Survey data

To assess tourists' satisfaction with the BCF event, positive values of the means difference (experience – expectation) reflected the degree of satisfaction while negative values represented the degree of dissatisfaction, and the average value of each factor was interpreted as a reflection of the degree of which factors tourists appreciate or which factors need to be improved. The results of the satisfaction of tourists are shown in Table 3. In Table 3 and Table 4, the sig. values of attributes for which we can significantly reject the null hypothesis were set in bold. As shown in Table 2, most of the positive attributes regarding cultural aspects have a mean expectation greater than 0. This implies that the expectations of visitors to BCF are generally positive because they did expect to enjoy good cultural values at the festival. In addition, by comparing the expectations and experiences, we could say that it appears tourists were highly and moderately satisfied with positive attributes regarding the cultural aspects of the BCF (6 out of 8 attributes). For example, the observed attribute 4 (*The Space of Gong Culture in the Central Highlands will be unique*) has means of 1.78 for expectation and of 2.73 for the experience; observed attribute 1 (*I will be able to visit historical sites*) has means of 2.04 for expectation and of 2.43 for the experience; and the variable 5 (*Traditional rites and festivals of local ethnic minorities will be interesting*) has means of 1.88 for expectation and of 2.36 for experience, indicating that tourists were highly satisfied. In addition, we do not have enough confidence to reject the null hypothesis for attribute 3 (*I will be able to visit the World Coffee Museum*), attribute 6 (*The street festival will be interesting*), and attribute 9 (*Cultural activities at the festival will be diverse*). Put differently, the means of expectation and experience of these attributes are not significantly different. Thus, the tourists were moderately satisfied with these attributes. However, the tourists were highly dissatisfied with 2 attributes, namely attribute 2 (*I will be able to participate in folk activities*) and attribute 7 (*The Buon Don Elephant Festival will be attractive*).

Table 3. Comparison between tourists' expectations and experiences regarding cultural aspects of the BCF.

No.	Statement	Expectation		Experience		Mean Diff.	T-Test	
		X	SD	X	SD		T _{value}	SIG
	<i>Positive attributes regarding cultural aspects</i>							
1	I will be able to visit historical sites	2.04	1.86	2.43	1.62	.388	2.41	.017
2	I will be able to participate in folk activities	1.41	1.73	1.03	2.06	-.388	-2.14	.034
3	I will be able to visit the World Coffee Museum	2.39	1.80	2.21	1.83	-.175	-1.02	.311
4	The Space of Gong Culture in the Central Highlands will be unique	1.78	1.68	2.73	5.90	.950	2.04	.044
5	Traditional rites and festivals of local ethnic minorities will be interesting	1.88	1.52	2.36	1.74	.488	3.06	.003
6	The street festival will be interesting	2.14	1.77	2.29	1.90	.150	0.84	.400
7	The Buon Don Elephant Festival will be attractive	1.70	1.71	1.24	2.04	-.463	-2.41	.017
8	Cultural activities at the festival will be diverse	1.74	1.74	1.68	1.79	-.063	-0.31	.753

Source: Authors' Calculation

In Table 4, the T-test results show that 5 negative attributes regarding environmental aspects are statistically significant (Sig. values < 5%). According to the analysis results, we found one surprising thing about the difference between expectations and perceptions, that is, all negative attribute groups are unsatisfactory values. The difference between the perception and expectation of this group is positive, indicating that tourists were not satisfied because what they received was more negative than their expectation (or the actual perception of visitors did not meet their expectations). They did not expect that the Festival would have such negative elements regarding environmental aspects as they received.

Table 4. Comparison between tourists' experience and expectation for negative attributes regarding environmental aspects of the BCF

No.	Statement	Expectation		Experience		Mean Diff.	T-Test	
		X	SD	X	SD		T _{value}	SIG
	<i>Negative attributes regarding the environment</i>							
1	There will be many beggars and street vendors	-1.70	2.02	0.13	2.53	1.825	7.13	.000
2	There will be a lack of public toilet facilities	-1.68	2.11	0.59	2.37	2.263	9.20	.000
3	There will be pollution in the city	-1.85	2.04	0.20	2.50	2.050	9.03	.000
4	There will be much garbage at the festival site	-1.64	1.82	0.68	2.10	2.313	11.78	.000
5	I will have to be careful about what I eat and drink at the festival	-0.93	2.14	0.08	2.05	1.000	4.03	.000

Source: Authors' Calculation

As shown in Table 4, tourists were highly dissatisfied with all negative attributes. Particularly, attribute 1 (*There will be many beggars and street vendors*), attribute 2 (*There will be a lack of public toilet facilities*), attribute 3 (*There will be pollution in the city*), and attribute 4 (*There will be much garbage at the festival site*) have high and positive values of mean difference indicating that tourists were very dissatisfied with these attributes. Finally, tourists were also disappointed with the food safety at the BCF. Therefore, BCF organizers should pay more attention to building more public toilets to meet the needs of BCF visitors (attribute 2); having stricter regulations on waste treatment (attributes 3 and 4); having stricter regulations to spare tourists from being disturbed by beggars, and to increase food safety at the BCF (attributes 1 and 5).

Conclusion

The satisfaction of tourists regarding cultural and environmental aspects of the BCF was analyzed in this paper. The findings from the HOLSAT model showed that tourists were not satisfied with 2 positive attributes related to cultural aspects and 5 negative ones regarding environmental protection at the festival. Therefore, the BCF organizers, tourism businesses, and policymakers should take measures to maintain, enhance or expand upon the positive attributes of the BCF regarding cultural aspects. In addition, plans for folk activities and elephant

festivals should be carefully revised to meet the expectation of tourists. The BCF organizers should also eliminate the negative points and weaknesses regarding the environment of the BCF.

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